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Summary and Conclusions

An error bound is derived for a reliability model approximation method. The approximation method is appropriate for the semi-Markov models of reconfigurable systems that are designed to achieve extremely high reliability. The semi-Markov models of these systems are complex, and a significant amount of their complexity arises from the detailed descriptions of the reconfiguration processes. The reliability model approximation method consists of replacing a detailed description of a reconfiguration process with the probabilities of the possible outcomes of the reconfiguration process. These probabilities are included in the model as instantaneous jumps from the fault-occurrence state. Since little time is spent in the reconfiguration states, instantaneous jumps are a close approximation to the original model. This approximation procedure is shown to produce an overestimation for the probability of system failure, and an error bound is derived for this overestimation.

Introduction

Efforts are being made to design reliable digital control systems using redundancy and reconfiguration. The reliability requirement for these systems can be extremely high. An example is the proposed requirement that the flight control system for a commercial aircraft have less than one chance in a billion of failure during a ten hour flight. Such requirements are beyond what can be established by natural life testing. An alternate method that is being considered is to compute the probability of system failure with a semi-Markov model that captures the elements of system architecture, component failure, and system recovery from failed components. One obstacle is that an accurate model of a redundant and reconfigurable digital system presents a major computational problem. A large number of states are necessary to represent the status of all the components in the system. The behavior of faulty components and the system recovery processes can be complex, multi-state transactions involving arbitrary probability distributions. The combination of slow fault occurrences and fast system recoveries in the same model creates stiff numerical equations.

One approach to this computation problem uses the model simplification and approximation technique known as instantaneous coverage which takes advantage of the structure of reliability models for reconfigurable systems [1,2,3]. In the system, there is first a fault occurrence which happens at a low constant rate. This fault occurrence is followed by a complex pattern of behavior that includes the behavior of the faulty component and the actions of the system to detect, identify, and remove the faulty component. If other components become faulty while the system is recovering from the first fault, the system may or may not have a coincident-fault failure. Coincident-fault failures depend on the design of the system and the location of the other fault occurrences. A desirable property is that the time from fault occurrence to removal of the faulty component be short since this reduces the likelihood

that additional fault occurrences will cause the system to fail. After all the faulty components have been removed, the system is in a fault-free state, and the cycle of fault occurrence and system recovery begins again. This cycle continues until the system fails from exhaustion of parts. Hence the model has fault-free states with slow fault-occurrence transitions and system-recovery states with fast transitions.

The instantaneous-coverage approximation first replaces all the transitions out of the system-recovery states with instantaneous jumps that have the "correct" probability. The "correct" probability is discussed in section five. This replacement is a close approximation because very little time is spent in the system-recovery states. The next step is to remove the system-recovery states which now have the instantaneous jumps. This removal can be performed in a manner that causes no error since zero time is spent in these states. This approach offers a reduction in model size and computational effort. In addition, because of the cyclic nature of the model-fault occurrence followed by a block of system recovery states--the model reduction can often proceed by stages with one block of system recovery states being removed at a time. This systematic removal is shown in the example in section three.

Sections three and four illustrate this procedure by examples. Section five proves that this procedure yields an overestimation for the probability of system failure. Section six derives an error bound for this overestimation in terms of the probabilities and means of the recovery distributions. Because of space limitations, only the more important points are covered and only a sketch of the proof is offered. In particular, there is no discussion of how to remove the instantaneous-jump states or how to obtain the probabilities or means of the recovery distributions.

This topic has received previous attention. An important paper [1] attempts to prove that instantaneous coverage produces an overestimation for the probability of system failure. The heart of the proof, however, consists of a result derived using control theory and this result is not true [4]. Another contribution to the field [2] offers conservative and optimistic bounds for an instantaneous-coverage model, not the original model. In particular, these results [2] do not discuss how close the instantaneous-coverage model is to the original model, and so do not give an error bound for the instantaneous-coverage approximation.

Assumptions, Notation, and Results

All reliability models satisfy four assumptions.

- (1) Fault occurrence transitions are constant rate processes.
- (2) System recovery transitions are semi-Markov processes.
- (3) There are a finite number of states in the model.
- (4) The initial state is a fault-free state.

The error bound is small if fault occurrence transitions are slow and recovery transitions are

fast, but these conditions are not necessary for the validity of the bound.

An effort has been made to use consistent mnemonics in all the figures. The conventions are

- A, B fault-free states
- R recovery-mode states
- C coincident-fault system failure states
- E exhaustion-of-parts system failure states
- J prefix for a state in an instantaneous-coverage model
- λ, γ component failure rates
- α, β intermittent fault on-and-off rates
- δ, ρ system recovery rates
- α_i, β_j component failure rates in the general model (Figure 7)
- f semi-Markov transition to a fault-free state
- g semi-Markov transition to a coincident-fault failure state.

The notation used for the statement of the error bound is

μ = maximum average transition time for all transitions out of a recovery-mode state

θ = maximum sum of the component failure rates out of any state

C_U = maximum probability of a transition to a failure state from a recovery-mode state

T = system operating time

$P\{k\}$ = probability that k or more events have occurred in a Poisson process with rate θ in the time interval from 0 to T.

The general error bound for converting to an instantaneous-jump reliability model is

$$ERRBND = \mu \theta C_U \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k P\{k-1\} + \mu \theta \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k P\{k\}. \quad (1)$$

Many systems have enough redundancy that three or more components must fail before there is system failure due to exhaustion of parts. In this case let N be the minimum number of components that must fail to cause system failure by exhaustion of parts, and assume that N is bigger than or equal to three. The error bound becomes

$$ERRBND = \mu \theta C_U \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} k P\{k-1\} + \mu \theta \sum_{k=N-1}^{\infty} k P\{k\}. \quad (2)$$

Illustrative Example for Computation and Methods of Proof

This section illustrates the contents of the theorems by considering a reconfigurable majority-voting fourplex subject to intermittent faults. A reliability model of this system is presented in Figure 1. The mnemonics are as described in section three. When a component fails, it is initially actively producing errors which means the fault can be detected and the faulty component removed from the system. When a component is actively faulty, it is detected and removed from the system at rate δ . When a fault is in a benign state, the faulty component is not producing errors which means the fault cannot be detected and removed from the system. A fault goes from active to benign at rate α and from benign to active at rate β . The system has a coincident fault failure if there are two faulty components in the system. The system has

Figure 1: Reliability Model of a Reconfigurable Fourplex With Intermittent Faults

an exhaustion of parts failure when the remaining good component fails.

There are three different ways to view the instantaneous jump version of the reliability model in Figure 1. Figure 2 displays the computational approach. In this approach, the recovery-mode states are treated separately as illustrated in Figure 2(a). The rate γ from states RA and RB to C is equal to 3λ or 2λ depending on whether the system is recovering from the first or second fault occurrence. Assuming that RA is the initial state in Figure 2(a), the term W, given in Figure 2(a), is the probability that the system removes the fault before another fault arrives. The term $1-W$, also given in Figure 2(a), is the probability that another fault arrives before the present fault is removed. These probabilities are computed assuming there is an infinite amount of time to traverse the model in Figure 2(a). Figure 2(b) shows the recovery-mode transitions replaced by instantaneous jumps, indicated by dotted lines. Since zero time is spent in the states R_1 and R_2 of Figure 2(b), these states can be removed from the model. The final version of the instantaneous jump procedure for computational purposes is shown in Figure 2(c).

The error bound for the conversion to instantaneous coverage is an expression with two terms. The terms bound the error introduced into the coincident-fault failure states and into the exhaustion-by-parts failure states. For the fourplex described above and for the parameter values $\lambda = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ /hour, $\delta = 1 \times 10^4$ /hour, $\alpha = \beta = 3600$ /hour, and an operating time of one hour, the calculations are

	Coincident-Fault Failure	Exhaustion-of-Parts Failure
ORIGINAL MODEL	2.398946×10^{-11}	1.9972×10^{-12}
INSTANTANEOUS COVERAGE MODEL	2.399759×10^{-11}	1.9996×10^{-12}
ERROR	8.13×10^{-15}	2.4×10^{-15}
ERROR BOUND	8.17×10^{-15}	1.3×10^{-14}

The error bound is computed using formula (2) from section three.

Figure 3 displays the model of the reconfigurable fourplex as seen for the proof that converting to instantaneous jumps produces an overestimation for the probability of failure. All the transitions out of the recovery-mode states have been converted to instantaneous jumps as indicated by the dotted lines. The proof consists of making two observations. The first is that the model in Figure 3 has the same

Figure 2(a): Recovery Model for the Intermittent Fault
 2(b): Reliability Model with Instantaneous Jumps for the Fourplex with Intermittent Faults
 2(c): Instantaneous Coverage Reliability Model for the Fourplex with Intermittent Faults

Figure 3: Reliability Model with Recovery Mode Transitions Replaced by Instantaneous Jumps

Figure 4: Reliability Model with Recovery Mode Transitions Replaced by Semi-Markov Transitions

paths from the initial state to the failure states as the model in Figure 1. The second is that the paths in Figure 3 are traversed more quickly than the paths in Figure 1.

Figure 4 displays the model as seen for the derivation of the error bound for converting to instantaneous jumps. This model suppresses all the internal information about fault recovery. It just displays the semi-Markov transitions from fault occurrence to either system recovery or system failure. The density functions f_i go from fault occurrence to system recovery and the density functions g_i go from fault occurrence to system failure. These functions are potentially very complex, but the only information needed about them is their probabilities and means. As mentioned before, the method of obtaining the probabilities and means is omitted because of the lack of space.

Example for Multiple-Fault Recovery

This section demonstrates the procedure for a system having a multiple-fault recovery model. Figure 5 displays the initial states for the Markov reliability model of a majority voting fiveplex. Figure 6 is a model of the same system where the multi-step constant-rate recovery transitions have been expressed as single-step semi-Markov transitions. It is easy to compute the probabilities of these semi-Markov transitions. For example, the transition g_1 to the system failure state C_1 in Figure 6 has the probability

$$\int_0^{\infty} g_1(t) dt = \frac{4\lambda}{4\lambda+\delta} \frac{3\lambda}{3\lambda+\rho} + \frac{4\lambda}{4\lambda+\delta} \frac{\rho}{3\lambda+\rho} \frac{3\lambda}{3\lambda+\delta}$$

The purpose of this fiveplex example in Figures 5 and 6 is to illustrate the generality of the model in Figure 7. A complex system can be modeled as a sequence of fault occurrences followed by recovery transitions.

Figure 5: Initial States of the Reliability Model for a Reconfigurable Majority Voting Fiveplex Showing the First Coincident-Fault Failure State C_1 and the Accompanying Successful Recovery States B_1 and B_2

Figure 6: Initial States of the Reliability Model for a Reconfigurable Majority-Voting Fiveplex with Semi-Markov Transitions out of the Recovery-Mode State R_1 into the Failure State C_1 and into the Successful-Recovery States B_1 and B_2

Derivation of the Conservativeness of Instantaneous Jumps

This section shows that converting some of the states in a semi-Markov reliability model to instantaneous-jump states leads to an upper bound for the probability of system failure. The proof uses the fact that there is a path from every state in the semi-Markov reliability model to an absorbing state representing system failure. The model has this feature because the system fails when a sufficient number of components fail and the states in the model represent (among other things) component failure.

Converting a state to an instantaneous-jump state means letting all the transitions out of the state become instantaneous jumps with the correct probability. The correct probability for a transition is the probability that the transition is made given an infinite amount of time. (Other choices for the correct probability are possible and are discussed later.)

The proof proceeds by considering all paths from the initial state to the absorbing states representing system failure. There are either a finite or countably infinite number of paths. The probability of system failure at time T can be computed by summing the probability of traversing each path by time T . The instantaneous-jump model has precisely the same paths as the original model. Hence the result can be obtained by showing that the probability of traversing each path in the instantaneous-jump model is greater than the probability of traversing the corresponding path in the original model.

Suppose a path in the original model consists of states $S_1, \dots, S_m, S_{m+1}, \dots, S_n$ where $m+1$ to n index the states that are to be converted to instantaneous-jump states. Since the model is semi-Markov, it is possible to rearrange the path so that these states are the last states in the path. This is done for notational convenience. Suppose h_i is the (possibly defective) transition density from state S_i to S_{i+1} . The probability of traversing this path by time T is

$$\int_0^T h_1(t_1) \dots \int_0^{T-t_1-\dots-t_{n-1}} h_n(t_n) \\ \int_0^{T-t_1-\dots-t_m} h_{m+1}(t_{m+1}) \\ \dots \int_0^{T-t_1-\dots-t_{n-2}} h_{n-1}(t_{n-1}) dt_{n-1} \dots dt_1$$

which is less than or equal to

$$\int_0^T h_1(t_1) \dots \int_0^{T-t_1-\dots-t_{n-1}} h_n(t_n) \\ \int_0^\infty h_{m+1}(t_{m+1}) \dots \int_0^\infty h_{n-1}(t_{n-1}) dt_{n-1} \dots dt_1.$$

The integrals from 0 to ∞ are the instantaneous jump probabilities used in the instantaneous-jump model. This proves the result.

It is possible to obtain an upper bound by integrating from 0 to T but it appears to be computationally more convenient to use the integral from 0 to ∞ .

Derivation of the Error Bound

This section outlines deriving the error produced by converting the recovery-mode states of a semi-Markov reliability model into instantaneous-jump states. The notation and bounds are given in section three. It is assumed that the model is in the form described in section one. That is, for any path through the model from the initial state to an absorbing failure state, the path begins with a slow fault-occurrence transition and then alternates between fast transitions out of a recovery-mode state and slow fault-occurrence transitions out of a fault-free state. The diagram for the derivation of the bound is shown in Figure 7.

Let JC_i be the state in the instantaneous-jump model that corresponds to the state C_i in Figure 7. Summing over the fan-out from state A gives

$$JC_1 - C_1 = \sum_{i=1}^m \int_0^T \alpha_i \exp(-\alpha t_1) \int_0^\infty g_i(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 \\ - \sum_{i=1}^m \int_0^T \alpha_i \exp(-\alpha t_1) \int_0^{T-t_1} g_i(t_2) dt_2 dt_1 \\ = \sum_{i=1}^m \int_0^T \alpha_i \exp(-\alpha t_1) \int_{T-t_1}^\infty g_i(t_2) dt_2 dt_1.$$

A little manipulation gives

$$JC_1 - C_1 = \mu \theta C_u.$$

In general,

$$JC_k - C_k \leq k \mu \theta C_u \text{ Poiss}\{k-1\}.$$

Summing all the bounds for $JC_k - C_k$ over k yields an error bound for the coincident-fault failure states of

$$\mu \theta C_u \sum_{k=1}^\infty k P\{k-1\}.$$

The error bound for the exhaustion of parts states is derived in a similar manner. A rather extensive amount of manipulation gives an error bound for these states of

$$\mu \theta \sum_{k=1}^\infty k P\{k\}.$$

The sum of the last two expressions give the total error bound in formula (1) in section three.

Figure 7: The Initial States of the Fan-out in a General Reliability Model for the Proof of the Error Bound for Instantaneous Coverage

Concluding Remarks

Converting the full reliability model into an instantaneous-coverage model is general and convenient. It handles complex fault behavior models in a side calculation. The final instantaneous-coverage model is a constant-rate Markov model even if the fault behavior model is more general. The results above show that this conversion leads to an overestimation for the probability of system failure. An error bound is derived for this overestimation.

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Biography

Allan L. White received a Ph. D. in mathematics from New Mexico State University. He has taught at the University of Colorado. He was an applied mathematician at Kentron International, Inc. He is now at NASA Langley Research Center. His interests include the design and analysis of reliable process control systems.